

STRESS ANALYSIS IN COMPRESSION LOADED RECTANGULAR COMPOSITE PLATES CONTAINING OPEN HOLE

Endel Iarve and Som Soni
AdTech Systems Research Inc.
1432 North Fairfield Road
Beavercreek OH 45432
USA

ABSTRACT

Independent cubic spline approximation of displacement and interlaminar stress components was used for three-dimensional stress analysis in finite composite plates containing an elliptical open hole. The method is capable of calculating all stress and strain components at any location through the plate including ply interfaces in practical composites containing numerous layers. Curvilinear coordinate transformation which mapped the plate with an opening onto simple rectangular region was introduced in terms of spline functions. The free edge boundary conditions were satisfied at the opening contour as natural boundary conditions. The desired accuracy of stress calculation was achieved by increasing the density of spline approximation nodal points. Stress analysis of a multidirectional 24-ply laminate made of AS4/3502 material with circular and elliptical holes was performed.

INTRODUCTION

Compression failure of composites containing an open hole is a complicated process involving delamination, microbuckling of fibres, and matrix cracking. An important issue in understanding this process is the identification of onset of failure. The delamination at the open hole edge on the early stages of compression loading when the failure initiates was indicated in several experimental studies [1,2]. To evaluate the possibility of the failure initiation due to delaminations at the free hole edge the three-dimensional stress analysis is required. In [3] a finite element formulation was given which assumes the transverse displacement through the thickness of the laminate to be constant. However, independent cross-sectional rotations of each layer were allowed. This approach actually didn't take into account the transverse strains and stresses directly. The results showed to be insensitive to changing the thickness to radius ratio when calculating transverse normal stresses.

A simplified approach for interlaminar stress calculation around the hole in cross-ply laminates was proposed in [4]. The following assumptions were accepted: (i) length and width of the laminate are much larger than the hole diameter; (ii) the distribution of in-plane stresses is uniform across the thickness of each ply; (iii) the affected area, associated with the interlaminar stresses, is limited to a distance of twice the laminate thickness from the hole edge. A similar idea of using the pre-assumed three-dimensional stress field was used in [5] to design "special-hole-elements". The results were obtained for $[90/0]_S$ and $[-45/45]_S$ laminates of an imaginary composite material.

Lucking et. al. [6] used a finite element method and substructuring approach to study the effect of geometry on interlaminar stresses in cross-ply symmetric composites with circular holes. 20 -node isoparametric displacement finite elements were used. Bi-cubic spline interpolation was utilized for obtaining the displacements in the nodes of sequentially used meshes. The results were obtained for $[0/90]_S$ infinite plate for different hole to thickness ratios.

Folias [7] has obtained a local asymptotic solution for three-dimensional stress fields in the immediate vicinity of a bonded interface and the free edge of a hole in a laminated composite

plate. It was shown that in case of isotropic plies the strength of singularity is uniform along the hole edge. It is indicated by the author that extension of this analysis to orthotropic laminates is also possible. In that case the strength of singularity will depend upon the coordinates of the point on the contour of the hole and the orientation of the ply material principal directions.

The present review shows a lack of accurate three-dimensional solution for calculating the stress-strain field in practical multilayered composites near open hole. On the other hand, the accurate asymptotic solutions are available only for laminates consisting of isotropic layers. The present work offers new approach to efficient computation of three-dimensional stresses in the vicinity of a hole in multilayered composites.

2.PROBLEM FORMULATION

A static linear elastic problem for a multilayered composite plate with a through the thickness opening, Figure 1, is considered. The plate consists of N orthotropic layers. In each layer, the orientation of principal material axis is defined relative to the x -axis. The angle between the x -axis and the direction of fibers for the k -th layer is counted counter-clockwise. The plate is of length L in x -direction and width A in y -direction. Thickness of a s -th ply is h_s and the coordinate of the interface between s -th and $(s+1)$ -th plies is

$$z^{(s)} = \sum_{k=1}^s h_k, \quad s=1, \dots, N, \quad z^{(0)}=0, \quad H = \sum_{s=1}^N h_s$$

The elliptical contour of the opening is defined in parametric form as

$$\begin{aligned} x &= a \cos \phi + x_c, \\ y &= b \sin \phi + y_c, \quad 0 \leq \phi \leq 2\pi \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where a and b are the radiuses of the ellipse and x_c, y_c - the opening center coordinates. Uniaxial loading in x - direction will be applied through the displacement boundary conditions at $x=0, L$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} u_x(0, y, z) &= \Delta, \quad u_x(L, y, z) = -\Delta \\ u_y(0, y, z) &= u_y(L, y, z) = u_z(0, y, z) = u_z(L, y, z) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The boundary conditions (2) are preferred to the stress boundary conditions in the laminate because of the different average stress in x -direction in the plies with different fiber orientations. $\Delta > 0$ introduces the compression loading and $\Delta < 0$ the tension loading. The unidirectional load or average applied stress can be obtained from

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{1}{H \cdot A} \int_0^H \int_0^A \sigma_{xx}(0, y, z) dy dz$$

The variational approach is chosen to formulate the problem for every ply. Interface continuity of the displacement components and transverse interlaminar stress components is applied.

3.METHOD OF SOLUTION

3.1 Curvilinear Transformation

The following transformation of the in-plane coordinates was proposed to map the plate with an opening onto a simple rectangular region.

$$\begin{aligned} x &= aF_1(r)\cos\phi + L \cdot F_2(r)\alpha(\phi) + x_c, \quad 0 \leq r \leq 1, \\ y &= bF_3(r)\sin\phi + A \cdot F_2(r)\beta(\phi) + y_c, \quad 0 \leq \phi \leq 2\pi. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The functions $F_1(r)$, $F_2(r)$, $F_3(r)$ upon the generalized curvilinear coordinate r satisfy the following boundary conditions :

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(0)=F_3(0)=1, F_2(0) &= 0, \\ F_1(1)=F_3(1)=0, F_2(1) &= 1. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

If $r=0$ then the transformation (3) describes the contour of the opening given in formula (1). For $r=1$ the transformation (3) describes parametric curve defined by second and third terms in the expressions for x and y . The functions $\alpha(\phi)$ and $\beta(\phi)$ of the generalized curvilinear coordinate ϕ are chosen so that for $r=1$ the transformation (3) gives the rectangular contour of the plate. Functions $F_1(r)$, $F_2(r)$, $F_3(r)$ and $\alpha(\phi)$, $\beta(\phi)$ are defined using cubic splines. Let us introduce following subdivisions:

$$\begin{aligned} 0=r_0 < r_1 < r_2 < r_3 \dots < r_m &= 1, \\ 0=\phi_0 < \phi_1 < \phi_2 < \phi_3 \dots < \phi_k &= 2\pi. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where m is the number of intervals in r direction and k is the number of intervals in ϕ direction. To provide the periodicity conditions at $\phi=0$ and $\phi=2\pi$ we extend the subdivision of ϕ -coordinate beyond the interval $[0,2\pi]$ by adding the nodes:

$$\phi_{-i} = \phi_{k-i} - 2\pi, \phi_{k+i} = \phi_i + 2\pi, i=1,2,3.$$

By use of the recurrent procedure for building the set of basic spline functions of arbitrary degree, given in [8], a set of basic cubic splines $\{\Phi_i(\phi)\}$, $i=1,\dots,k+3$ and a set of non-periodic splines $\{R_i(r)\}$, $i=1,\dots,m+3$ are obtained. The five functions in transformation (3) are represented as

$$F_i(r) = \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} f_{ij} R_j(r), i=1,2,3, \quad \alpha(\phi) = \sum_{j=1}^{m+3} \alpha_j \Phi_j(\phi), \quad \beta(\phi) = \sum_{j=1}^{m+3} \beta_j \Phi_j(\phi). \quad (6)$$

Where f_{ij} , α_j and β_j are numerical coefficients defining the shape of transformation functions and providing the boundary conditions (4). Figure 2.a shows the $F_1(r)$, $F_2(r)$, $F_3(r)$ functions, Figure 2.b shows $\alpha(\phi)$, $\beta(\phi)$ functions and Figure 2.c shows the coordinate lines $r=\text{const}$ and $\phi=\text{const}$ for a plate with elliptical hole. Following parameters were used $L=3A$, $a=2.4b$, $a=0.2L$, $x_c=L/2$, $y_c=A/2$, the subdivision given in formula (5) was uniform and $m=16$, $k=24$. The increasing density of subdivision near the hole edge is provided by using appropriate coefficients in equation (6) rather than by non-uniform subdivision in r and ϕ -coordinate directions.

3.2 Spline Approximation of Displacement and Interlaminar Stress Components

The following solution will obtain the displacement components relative to xyz -coordinates as functions of r , ϕ and z . To write the three-dimensional spline approximation of displacements we need to introduce splines upon z -coordinate. To do so we subdivide the thickness of every ply into n_s intervals, where $s=1,\dots,N$ - total number of plies in the plate :

$$z^{(s-1)}=z_0 < z_1 < z_2 < \dots < z_{n_s}=z^{(s)}, s=1,\dots,N. \quad (7)$$

The three-dimensional spline approximation of the displacement components in the s -th ply can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
u_x^{(s)}(r,\phi,z) &= \sum_{i=1}^{m+3} \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} \sum_{l=1}^{n_s+3} u_{ijl}^{(s)} R_i(r) \Phi_j(\phi) Z_l(z) \\
u_y^{(s)}(r,\phi,z) &= \sum_{i=1}^{m+3} \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} \sum_{l=1}^{n_s+3} v_{ijl}^{(s)} R_i(r) \Phi_j(\phi) Z_l(z) \\
u_z^{(s)}(r,\phi,z) &= \sum_{i=1}^{m+3} \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} \sum_{l=1}^{n_s+3} w_{ijl}^{(s)} R_i(r) \Phi_j(\phi) Z_l(z)
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

were $\{Z_l(z)\}$, $l=1,\dots,n_s+3$ is the set of non-periodic cubic basic spline functions in z-direction. The modification of this general form of the three-dimensional spline approximation of displacements in order to satisfy the boundary conditions at the plate boundaries, given by formula (1), was discussed in [8] and will not be considered here. Independent approximation of the interlaminar traction components on the interface $z=z^{(s)}$ between (s-1)-th and s-th plies can be written as following

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{zz}^{(s)}(r,\phi) &= \sum_{i=1}^{m+3} \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} p_{ij}^{(s)} R_i(r) \Phi_j(\phi) \\
\tau_{zx}^{(s)}(r,\phi) &= \sum_{i=1}^{m+3} \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} \tau_{ij}^{(s)} R_i(r) \Phi_j(\phi) \\
\tau_{zy}^{(s)}(r,\phi) &= \sum_{i=1}^{m+3} \sum_{j=1}^{k+3} \eta_{ij}^{(s)} R_i(r) \Phi_j(\phi)
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

We will assume that the facial surfaces are traction free, i.e.

$$p_{zz}^{(0)} = p_{zz}^{(N)} = \tau_{zx}^{(0)} = \tau_{zx}^{(N)} = \tau_{zy}^{(0)} = \tau_{zy}^{(N)} = 0. \tag{10}$$

The deformation energy of the s-th ply can be written as

$$P^{(s)} = \int_{z^{(s-1)}}^{z^{(s)}} dz \int_0^1 dr \int_0^{2\pi} \vec{\varepsilon}^{*} C^{(s)} \vec{\varepsilon} \det \mathbf{J} \, d\phi \tag{11}$$

where $\vec{\varepsilon}^* = (\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{zz}, \varepsilon_{zy}, \varepsilon_{zx}, \varepsilon_{xy})$ contains the strain components relative to xyz-coordinates expressed through r, ϕ and z , $C^{(s)}$ is a 6 by 6 modulus matrix of the s-th ply in xyz-coordinates and \mathbf{J} - is the Jacobian matrix of the transformation (3). The superscript star means transpose of the vector. The work of the surface tractions in the s-th ply can be accounted for as following

$$\begin{aligned}
T^{(s)} = \int_0^1 dr \int_0^{2\pi} \{ & p_{zz}^{(s)} u_z^{(s)}(r,\phi,z^{(s)}) - p_{zz}^{(s-1)} u_z^{(s)}(r,\phi,z^{(s-1)}) + \tau_{zx}^{(s)} u_x^{(s)}(r,\phi,z^{(s)}) - \tau_{zx}^{(s-1)} u_x^{(s)}(r,\phi,z^{(s-1)}) + \\
& \tau_{zy}^{(s)} u_y^{(s)}(r,\phi,z^{(s)}) - \tau_{zy}^{(s-1)} u_y^{(s)}(r,\phi,z^{(s-1)}) \} \det \mathbf{J} \, d\phi
\end{aligned}$$

To satisfy the displacement continuity conditions at the interlaminar surfaces $s=1,\dots,N-1$ we require in equations (8) that

$$u_{ij(n_s+3)}^{(s-1)} = u_{ij0}^{(s)}, v_{ij(n_s+3)}^{(s-1)} = v_{ij0}^{(s)}, w_{ij(n_s+3)}^{(s-1)} = w_{ij0}^{(s)}, \quad i=1,\dots,m+3, \quad j=1,\dots,k+3$$

All the independent displacement and traction spline approximation coefficients now can be obtain from the principle of the minimum potential energy

$$\delta \left\{ \sum_{s=1}^N (P^{(s)} + T^{(s)}) \right\} = 0. \quad (12)$$

3.3 Interlaminar Stress Calculation

The interlaminar stresses at the ply interface $z=z^{(s)}$ can be directly calculated from equations (9) after the coefficients $P_{ij}^{(s)}, \tau_{ij}^{(s)}, \eta_{ij}^{(s)}$ were obtained from (12). To calculate the stress components in any other location of the s -th ply we first obtain the displacement spline approximation coefficients from (12), then we obtain the strain components $\vec{\epsilon}$ with respect to xyz -coordinates as functions of r, ϕ and z and calculate the stress components $\vec{\sigma} = (\sigma_{xx}, \sigma_{yy}, \sigma_{zz}, \sigma_{zy}, \sigma_{zx}, \sigma_{xy})$ from the Hook's law $\vec{\sigma} = C^{(s)} \vec{\epsilon}$ (13)

An alternative approximation of the interlaminar stress components can be obtained by calculating these stresses using the Hook's law (13). In this case we have two values for every interlaminar stress component for any location at the interface. One value is obtained by approaching the interface from the upper ply and the other by approaching the interface from the lower ply. For the exact displacement field, these two values must be equal. Practically, due to the approximation error, these values are unequal. A parametric study showed that the interlaminar stress value obtained by using the traction formula (9) and those by using Hook's law (13) converge to each other by increasing the number of sublayers through the thickness. Thus using finer subdivisions of the layers, continuity of the transverse interlaminar stress components at the interfaces between plies can be achieved with any given accuracy.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

4.1 Verification Study

The comparative study showed a good agreement of the in-plane stress components prediction at the hole edge for $[90/0]_S$ and $[-45/45]_S$ laminates with those in references [3,5,9]. Knowing that the transverse interlaminar stresses are singular at the hole boundary we expect the stress values to grow infinitely by using more and more dense in-plane mesh. However, by increasing the number of sublayers through the thickness of every layer, for a fixed in-plane mesh the interlaminar stresses converge to a certain finite limit. The interlaminar stresses shown in Figure 3 are obtained in $[-45/45]_S$ laminate at the edge of a circular hole $a=b=25\text{mm}$ in the center of a $0.5 \times 0.25\text{m}^2$ plate by using the in-plane mesh given in equation (5) with $m=16$ and $k=20$. The ply properties are same as in [3,5,9]: $E_1 = 207 \text{ GPa}, E_2 = E_3 = 20.7 \text{ GPa}, G_{13} = G_{23} = G_{12} = 10 \text{ GPa}, \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{12} = 0.336, h=5\text{mm}$. The polar angle θ at the the hole edge is simply related to the ϕ - coordinate as $\theta=180\phi/\pi$ and counted counterclock-wise from the x -axis. $\tau_{z\theta}$ refers to the stress value calculated from relations (9); $\sigma_{z\theta}(45)$ refers to computations using Hook's law given in equation (13) using the $+45^\circ$ layer properties and $\sigma_{z\theta}(-45)$ represents that for -45° layer. The results obtained by using 3 sublayers through the thickness of the ply give the stress value calculated as a traction significantly higher then the values obtained using Hook's law. By using 8 sublayers through the thickness of the ply the stress calculated by two approaches practically coincide. It is remarkable that the stress values obtained through formula (9) are very close for the two out-of-plane subdivisions. An important observation was made that the interlaminar stress value obtained as the traction decreases and the values obtained using Hook's law increase until they become equal by increasing the number of sublayers. The difference between these two stress values can be used as the measure of the accuracy of the interlaminar stress prediction for given number of sublayers.

4.2 Stress Analysis of 24-ply AS4/3502 Laminate with Elliptical Hole

A 24-ply symmetric AS4/3502 laminate $[\pm 45/90/0/(0/\pm 45/0)]_S$ is considered under an in-plane uniaxial compressive load. The plate is 75mm long, 25mm wide and 3mm thick. Two types

of single central openings are considered: circular hole 6.35mm in diameter and elliptical hole with $a=15\text{mm}$ and $b=6.35\text{mm}$. The following ply properties are used: $E_1 = 144 \text{ GPa}$, $E_2 = E_3 = 8.28 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{23} = 2.9 \text{ GPa}$, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 4.83 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{23} = 0.37$, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{12} = 0.35$.

Figure 4.a shows the normal stress component σ_{11} in fiber direction at the hole edge for two plies with highest stress concentration. Ply number and its orientation are shown in the legend. The plies are counted from the mid-surface. The maximum compression stress concentration was found to be $8.54\sigma_0$ at the edge of the circular hole and $4.8\sigma_0$ at the edge of the elliptical hole at mid-surface.

The transverse interlaminar stresses were examined to determine the possibility of the onset of damage due to delamination. Figure 4.b shows the interlaminar shear stresses σ_{13} at the hole edge. The horizontal solid lines τ_{ult}^{ellips} and τ_{ult}^{circ}

$$\tau_{ult}^{ellip} = 4.8 \frac{S}{X}, \quad \tau_{ult}^{circ} = 8.54 \frac{S}{X}$$

indicate the value of the transverse shear stresses equal to allowable $S = 93 \text{ MPa}$, provided that the stress in fiber direction σ_{11} has reached its allowable value $X = 1450 \text{ MPa}$, i.e. when the applied load is $\sigma_0 = X/4.8$ for elliptical hole and $\sigma_0 = X/8.54$ for the circular. The maximum values of interlaminar shear stress are close for both hole shapes and occur at the interfaces between $45^\circ/0^\circ$ and $-45^\circ/0^\circ$ at approximately $\pm 70^\circ$ and $\pm 110^\circ$ directions for circular and $\pm 55^\circ$ and $\pm 125^\circ$ for elliptical hole.

The extended regions where the interlaminar shear stresses exceed τ_{ult}^{ellips} and τ_{ult}^{circ} values indicate that the interlaminar shear stresses are exceeding their static allowable values even before any other stress components have reached their allowables. The detailed investigation revealed high in-plane tensile stresses in the direction perpendicular to fibers at approximately same locations as the transverse shear stress concentration. The indicated locations are likely to be the failure initiation zones and the initial failure mode are delamination and matrix cracking. These zones of weakened matrix are the locations of fiber local buckling leading to the catastrophic failure.

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Figure 1. The multilayered plate with elliptical opening

Figure 2. (a),(b)-Curvilinear transformation functions and (c)-coordinate lines

Figure 3. Interlaminar shear stress in $[-45/45]_s$ laminate.

Figure 4. Stress components in 24-ply laminate: (a) Stresses in fiber direction, (b) interlaminar shear stress.